

**THE ROLE OF MODERN MANAGEMENT IN THE FIELD OF
ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN AND THE PROBLEMS OF ITS
IMPLEMENTATION.**

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Annotation: This article describes the current state of management in Uzbekistan, the problems and prospects for the introduction of modern management in business.

Keywords: Economics, management, entrepreneurship, traditional management, modern management, economics, management, profit, integrated approach, consensus, prosperity, Japanese experience.

It is not difficult to imagine that in a market economy there are thousands of enterprises based on different ownership. The organization of the management of enterprises to one degree or another depends on the management skills of the head of the enterprise. His ability is measured by the extent to which he has mastered the knowledge in the field of management. In this context, the word management has become one of the words that has entered our lives in connection with the market economy.

Management is a word with a wide range of meanings, with many different meanings, and management is the management of the world. The market environment itself assesses the success of the organization, regulation, coordination, control of the production process and the degree to which the set goals are achieved. As the scale of production expands and the amount of resources in supply increases, so do the tasks of management.

Of course, today's modern enterprises are abandoning traditional management and prioritizing modern management. Because these management systems are drastically different from each other.

Traditional management is an approach to project management that suits many industries and conditions. This approach uses traditional tools and methods to manage and solve problems. This control system includes the following functions:

- Planning
- Establishment
- Management

Modern management is a unique function, a unique tool for organizations to produce results. Fulfilling this super task requires an expansion of the manager's area of responsibility, which includes all the factors that affect the organization's operations and its results:

Today, the functions of modern management include:

- Planning;
- to establish;
- motivation;
- management;
- coordination;

Modern management is a strategic approach at all levels of management, where the human factor is used as the main factor. The following management principles are outlined:

one hundred percent personal responsibility of the manager; advanced communication at all levels;

continuous training of staff and managers;

the atmosphere in the enterprise helps employees to develop their skills to the maximum;

each employee consciously contributes to the overall outcome;

rejection of authoritarian leadership style in favor of leadership;

advanced communication skills to communicate with customers;

business ethics;

openness and trust in people;

knowledge of the basics of management and their use;

clearly imagine the path of the enterprise;

desire to constantly improve themselves and improve the quality of their work;

k complex approach.

It is not easy to put all of these principles into practice, but many modern businesses are striving for innovation. Many developed countries now use modern management. Each also has its own management system. They use unique methods to approach

problem areas. Although the United States and Europe have the upper hand, Japanese managers have surprised the West and the East with their sharply different governance principles. Typically, they rely on a method known as “ consensus ” when making decisions about problematic situations

. Consensus is a system of understanding what a decision is about, rather than what the decision will be, by taking action and discussing with all other employees, taking into account all the risks and consequences of the decision, without rushing to make a decision. In this system, the decision-making process is slow, but the implementation process is very fast and efficient. The diagram below clearly shows that this system of governance in Japan is sufficiently effective and competes with the United States in this regard.

(Figure 1)

Profit-to-earnings ratio of the United States and Japan for 2010-2019

Extensive work has been carried out in Uzbekistan over the years to improve modern management. However, the development of this industry and the use of modern governance principles in developed countries still lack attention. It should be noted that in order to develop this sector, it is necessary, first of all, to train modern personnel with foreign experience, to mobilize them to study foreign experience. The revolutionary implementation of Japan's famous " consensus " principle and other important management methods of other developed countries into our economy can play a key role in solving this problem.

Indeed, at a time when the development of science and technology has reached its peak, the demand for modern specialists in the labor market is growing day by day. As the production strategy and working conditions of enterprises change, so do the requirements for the character of specialists. The large-scale introduction of new equipment and technologies into production requires from today's generation of advanced personnel the skills to quickly master the techniques and technologies and understand their secrets, as well as high intellectual potential. In line with the high level of demand for such personnel, competition among professionals will also be strong. In the competitive struggle in the labor market, only high quality can win. In this regard, the system of management of specialists at the level of demand also needs to be improved accordingly. Proper management of the human factor in the production process is also an art.

Improving the quality of education standards and human capital is an objective necessity in a developed economy. At the same time, in the context of improving the system of higher education and the growing demand for skilled workers, an in-depth analysis of world experience in this area, the main directions of radical improvement of retraining and management in our country determination is important. It should be noted that one of the priorities in this regard is to further improve the measures taken in our country to ensure the balance and mutually beneficial cooperation between education and industry. In order to establish enterprises in our country equipped with high equipment and technology, operating in accordance with modern requirements and world standards, and to gain a foothold in the world market with our national brand, it is necessary to pay serious attention to personnel management in enterprises. is compatible. This is because the satisfaction of the workers and employees of the enterprise is the most important and guaranteed force that motivates them to unite in the pursuit of a common goal, to work sincerely for the development and prospects of the enterprise. Conclusion

The role of management in the economy of Uzbekistan is urgent. Improving the skills of today's staff, understanding the secrets of modern management , guarantees a high level of success in the future. Therefore, understanding the essence of the content of this field and becoming a mature professional based on deep interest and action is described as a necessary factor for today.

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